

Cold sintered PVDF polymer – $Ba_{1-x}Sr_xTiO_3$ based ceramic nanocomposites for high energy storage application

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Abstract:

The objective of current work is to study the ferroelectric ceramic $Ba_{0.7}Sr_{0.3}TiO_3$ (BST) –PVDF (Polyvinylidene fluoride) Polymer nanocomposites for energy storage applications. Fairly dense composites have been synthesized using recently invented cold sintering process (CSP) (1, 2) and their dielectric and energy storage properties have been investigated. CSP is a new sintering technique to achieve dense ceramics at extraordinary low temperature ($<200^{\circ}C$), providing opportunity to fabricate high content ceramic nanocomposites with polymer reinforcements. Dense samples of BST-PVDF nanocomposites have been prepared below $180^{\circ}C$ (at low temperature) with 80% ceramic as a matrix and 20% PVDF as Nano fillers. XRD analysis has been performed. High resolution SEM analysis has been performed which confirms the formation of PVDF coated BST ceramic grains. Energy storage capacity has been qualitatively analysed using P – E hysteresis curves.

Keywords: Cold Sintering, Ferroelectric, Nanocomposites.

References:

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